

Sources of finance and performance of small and medium enterprises

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Abstract

This study examines the relationship between access to finance and performance of micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs) in Gwagwalada area of Abuja. Specifically, this study examines the relationship between commercial bank loans and performance of MSMEs. Also, this study seeks to know the relationship between Microfinance bank loans and performance of MSMEs. The researcher obtained data from primary and secondary sources. In all, 180 questionnaires were considered valid for analysis. The researcher made use of simple random sampling techniques and descriptive and Pearson correlation to test the hypotheses. The findings demonstrate a positive but insignificant relationship between access to finance and financial performance of MSMEs. This result suggests that availability of funds enhances MSMEs financial performance but access to finance is not the only variable that may influence MSMEs performance. Further, results indicate a positive relationship between commercial bank loans, microfinance bank loans and MSMEs performance. Hence, the present study concludes that the importance of finance in the life of an enterprise cannot be over-emphasized because a firm without adequate funds to operate will experience a limited growth. This study recommends among other things that, there is a need to strengthen the Microfinance institutions to make them more readily available to assist MSMEs owners financially.

Keywords: MSMEs performance, commercial bank loans, microfinance banks, economic growth and development.

Introduction

Worldwide, small and medium enterprises (SMEs) are regarded as the lubricants for the engine of socioeconomic growth and development (Amin, Thurasamy, Aldakhil & Kaswuri, 2016; Gbandi & Amisah, 2021; Uwajumogu, Nwokoye, Anochiwa, & Ojike, 2024). SMEs play pivotal role in the economic transformation of both developed and developing countries because they stimulate business activities in both commercial and rural locations, reduce poverty by means of job creation,

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encourage even distribution of wealth, and increase the local value additions (National Bureau of Statistics-NBS, 2023). Hence, SMEs promote indigenous industrial transformation through the mobilization and utilization of local savings, local raw material, and human capital to engage in local production of goods and services. Also, SMEs serve as sources of inputs to large enterprises (Uwajumogu, Nwokoye, Anochiwa, & Ojike, 2024; Ilegbinosa & Jumbo, 2023).

On average, in developed economies (high income countries), SMEs contribute 55% and 65% to Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and employment, respectively. In developing countries, middle income countries to be specific, SMEs on average contribute 70% to GDP and 95% to total employment. Similarly, in low income economies, they contribute 60% to GDP and 70% to total employment (Hendrickson, 2019; SMEDAN, 2024).

Further, Rodríguez-Gutiérrez, Moreno, and Tejada (2023) reported that SMEs account for between 90 to 99 percent of the private sector enterprises globally.

A look at African countries such as Morocco revealed that 93 percent of private firms are SMEs (Edinburgh Group, 2019) while in Ghana, about 92 percent are SMEs. Similarly, 91 percent of registered businesses in South Africa are SMEs and provide about 61 percent of employment. Meanwhile in Ghana, SMEs generate about 85 percent of employment in the manufacturing sector (Osmond & Paul, 2016). while in Nigeria, about 96 percent of business enterprises are SMEs with little contribution to employment generation as government remains the major employer of labour in Nigeria (SMEDAN, 2019, 2024). Evidence abounds that the performance of SMEs in Nigeria is not as the performance of SMEs in other developing countries such as South Africa, Ghana, and

Malaysia (Du & Banwo, 2023; Ofili, 2023). The low level of MSMEs' performance in the country has negative effect on the GDP, growth rate, unemployment rate, and Nigeria's ranking on the world competitiveness index.

Further, the position of Nigeria in terms of global competition is very poor. Evidence in the global competitiveness index (GCI) shows that Nigeria ranked 115 out of 144 countries (World Economic Forum, 2019). Similarly, in 2024 the same GCI indicated that Nigeria's global competitiveness ranking dropped from 115 in 2019 to 127 in 2024 out of 144 countries (World Economic Forum, 2023) while African countries such as Mauritius, South Africa, Rwanda, Morocco, Botswana, Algeria, and Tunisia were ranked ahead of Nigeria.

Although MSMEs are found in different sectors of the economy, the researcher is of the opinion that the agricultural and real sector (manufacturing) deserve further attention in Nigeria if Nigeria is to fully actualize her developmental goals. Furthermore, a look at the contribution of the manufacturing and agricultural sectors to GDP in Nigeria is worrisome and deserves attention.

In Nigeria, about 59% of SMEs have reported difficulties in accessing financial services (Bature *et al.*, 2018). Also, about 77% of the MSMEs in Nigeria have indicated that lack of access to financial resources is a major problem hindering their performance (Ayanda & Laraba, 2011). A substantial number of MSMEs finance their businesses using personal savings rather than finances from the government, banks and other financial institutions. Accordingly, over 54% use personal savings, family savings 16.7%, cooperatives 6.9%, while only 22% have access to finance from the government, banks and other financial intuitions (SMEDAN, 2024). The MSMEs' lack of

finance in Nigeria continues to be a major issue to their development, as the percentage of a successful applicant for the finance is very low (NPC, 2011; SMEDAN, 2024). In addition, the small percentages of SMEs that are successful are required to pay a high cost of borrowing of about 30% interest rate and collateral requirements (African Development Bank Group, 2018). Since available literature indicates that most MSMEs use personal savings and financial contributions from friends to finance their businesses, little is known about debt finance in running business operations. Hence, this study shall focus on the relationship between debt finance (loans from commercial banks, loans from Microfinance banks, and venture capital) and performance of MSMEs in the manufacturing and industrial sector.

Conceptual Review

Concept of Firm Performance

Richard (2008) defined performance as incorporating three specific areas of organization results: financial performance, product market performance and shareholder return. In the study by Lusthaus et al., (2002) firm performance can be seen in terms of the followings: effectiveness defined as the ability of the firm to attain its objectives vis-à-vis those competitors in the same market, eg. Sales growth and market share. Efficiency: accuracy, how economically the organization can turn resources/inputs into results, financial viability: ability to nurture required funds and relevance: adaptive to the stakeholders and its environment. Tangen (2003) argued that organizational performance measures as metrics selected to measure the efficiency and/or effectiveness of an accomplishment/achievement by the business organization.

Firm performance is a multi-dimensional construct which can be evaluated through financial and non-financial measures (Zhou, Hu & Shi, 2023; Amin, Thurasamy, Aldakhil & Kaswuri, 2016). These measures of firm performance (particularly financial measures) can be determined objectively from documented past records and can also be determined subjectively through self-reported perception held about the firm.

From a business perspective, firms achieve their objectives when they profitably satisfy their stakeholders' needs more than their competitors. For a firm to achieve this superior performance, the goals and objectives of the firm must be achieved in an efficient and effective way compared to its competitors.

For the sake of simplicity, the present study conceptualized SME performance as the ability of an SME to effectively and efficiently utilize the available resources to survive, satisfy customers' needs, and contribute to the creation of employment. Also, SME performance means the financial and non-financial outcome of the efforts of SMEs in achieving their stated goals and objectives.

Sources of Finance

Finance is viewed as the availability of financial resources from both internal and external sources such as all forms of loan, equipment leasing, financial services, trade credit from suppliers, owners' equity or business partners (Kelley, Singer, & Herrington, 2012). According to Kasseeah, Ancharaz and Tandrayen-Ragoobur (2019), availability of financial resource is critical to the survival of any business ventures. Hence, Adomako, Danso, and Damoah (2016) found that SMEs' ability to develop dynamic organizational capabilities to a certain extent, depends on availability

of funds. Fatoki (2021) sees access to debt finance as the gap that exists between the firm's need for financial resources and the actual supply of financial resources.

Practically, SMEs' lack of finance in Nigeria continues to be a major issue to their development, as the percentage of successful applicants for loan is very low (SMEDAN, 2018). In addition, the small percentage of SMEs that are successful are required to pay a high cost of borrowing close to 30% interest rate and stringent collateral requirements (African Development Bank Group, 2019).

Theoretical Review

The RBV postulates that the basis for competitive advantage of a firm depends on the firm's ability to utilize the available bundle of valuable intangible and tangible resources (Barney, 1991; Wernerfelt, 1984). It is argued that these resources must be valuable, rare, inimitable and non-substitutable (VRIN) resources (Barney, 1991). To be specific, the RBV emerged as the theory that explains firm performance, which is driven by resources that are heterogeneous rather than market power.

There are two fundamental assertions of the RBV. Firstly, assets, capabilities, procedures, characteristics and knowledge possessed by the firm are different from its competitor (heterogeneity). Secondly, the difference may be for a long time i.e., immobility of the resources is sustained for a long time (Barney, 1991). Heterogeneity is needed for a firm to achieve competitive advantage. The resources possessed must not be owned by its competitors at least for some period while immobility of resources refers to the difficulty faced by the competitors in

copying the strategy of the firm that possesses the resources. This study concludes that finance is a resource and has the tendency to influence firm's financial performance.

Finance and MSMEs Performance

Generally, access to finance is vital for the growth and development of business enterprises (Kasseeah, Ancharaz & Tandrayen-Ragoobur, 2019). However, evidence abounds in the literature that prominent among the challenges facing small business enterprises across the globe, but most especially African countries is access to finance (Kyophilavong, 2011; Mohammed & Obeleagunzelibe, 2021; OECD, 2017; Singer, Aromos & Arreola 2023). This implies that the accessibility and availability of financial resources will go a long way to positioning businesses strategically to build the needed capabilities to deliver superior performance and consequently fulfil their role of socioeconomic growth and development of nations

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According to Mazanai and Fatoki (2017) and Batra, Kaufmann, and Stone (2018), access to finance is directly related to the performance of SMEs. Thus, the lack of finance adversely affects the full potential of SMEs as an economic driver. However, it has been reported that most SMEs in

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developing economies are restricted in accessing finances, though the opaque nature of the firm may result in serious constraints of accessing external financing and consequently affect their performance (Beck, Demirgüç-Kunt, & Maksimovic, 2008). Access to finance refers to the lack of internally generated funds and financial services by financial institutions, high cost of capital, lack of financial knowledge, high administration costs, high collateral requirements and inexperienced financial intermediaries (SMEDAN, 2018). Several studies indicate that productivity of small businesses depends largely on its access to capital (Frank, Kessler, & Fink, 2022; Zampetakis, Vekini, & Moustakis, 2011).

Few studies demonstrated that a firm's superior performance may be attributed to the ability of the firm to access required funds (Ayyagari, Demirgu-Kunt, & Maksimovic, 2008; Frank et al., 2022; Kyophilavong, 2011). Similarly, Batra et al. (2017) stated that access to finance enhances a firm's growth and development, which implies that access to financial facilities, may have a positive effect on overall economic performance of SMEs. Overall, small businesses perform better when they have access to finance. In other words, access to capital is essential to small businesses' performance (Wiklund & Shepherd, 2005; Steinerowska-Streb & Steiner, 2021).

Methods

Research design

This research is quantitative in nature due to its ability to elicit data from a large population. Survey design was considered appropriate for this study. Hence, it was adopted in examining the role of access to finance on performance of MSMEs. More so, the study is a cross-sectional

Population

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The area covered in this study is Gwagwalada, Abuja. Specifically, micro, small and medium enterprises owners who have benefited from loan facilities from commercial banks. In all, 341 MSMEs owner/managers make-up the study’s population. Using Krejcie and Morgan (1970) sample determination table, 181 is the appropriate sample for the present study. Likert scale method was used to design the questionnaire using agreement-disagreement continuum ranging from “strongly disagreed (1)” to “strongly agree (5)”. The researcher administered 220 copies of the questionnaire to compensate for non-response or low response from the participants.

Analysis

The study used Cronbach’s alpha to test the study reliability test while Pearson Correlations Coefficients was employed to test the hypotheses. Analysis was based on 180 valid questionnaires returned.

Results

Multicollinearity test, model fit, and ANOVA test results proved that the model is statistically significant. Table 1 shows the result of the Pearson correlation.

Table 1 Correlations

		Financial Performance
Access to Finance	Pearson Correlation	.138
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.065
	N	180
Commercial Bank Loan	Pearson Correlation	.196**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.009
	N	180

Microfinance Bank Loan	Pearson Correlation	-.273**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	180
Venture Capital	Pearson Correlation	.508**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	180

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**.. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Discussion of Results

The first research hypothesis stated that there is no relationship between access to finance and financial performance of MSMEs. The result of Pearson correlation in table 1 shows that access to finance and MSMEs financial performance have positive Pearson correlation coefficient value of .138 but have no significant relationship with p - value of $.065 > \alpha = 0.05$. This result revealed that access to finance does not influence MSMEs financial performance and so, has no significant relationship with financial performance. The result disagreed with most existing studies. This implies that it is not only finance that is needed for an impressive financial performance, other variables may be important such as SMEs' owners' competence, capability, ability, and environmental conditions.

The second research hypothesis stated that there is no relationship between commercial bank loans and financial performance of MSMEs. The result of Pearson correlation in table 1 shows that commercial bank loans and MSMEs financial performance have positive Pearson correlation coefficient value of .196 and a significant relationship with p - value of $.009 < \alpha = 0.05$. This result revealed that commercial bank loans influence MSMEs financial performance and so, has significant relationship with financial performance.

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The third research hypothesis stated that there is no relationship between microfinance bank loans and financial performance of MSMEs. The result of Pearson correlation in table 1 shows that microfinance bank loans and MSMEs financial performance have negative Pearson correlation coefficient value of $-.273$ and a significant relationship with p - value of $.000 < \alpha = 0.05$. This result revealed that microfinance bank loans influence MSMEs financial performance and so, has significant relationship with financial performance. This result agrees with reality in Nigeria. We have seen instances where Micro Finance banks lent money to SMEs owners. The business do perform well but with difficulties in repaying back micro finance loans. By the micro finance banks will forcefully recover their loans, the SMEs will go back to point zero.

The fourth research hypothesis stated that there is no relationship between venture capital and financial performance of MSMEs. The result of Pearson correlation in table 1 shows that venture capital and MSMEs financial performance have positive Pearson correlation coefficient value of $.508$ and a significant relationship with p - value of $.000 < \alpha = 0.05$. This result revealed that venture capital influence MSMEs financial performance positively and so, has significant relationship with financial performance.

Conclusion

The present study has demonstrated a positive relationship between some forms of finance and financial performance of MSMEs. This suggests that every MSMEs needs sufficient funds to operate and succeed. Bearing in mind that finance is the backbone of every enterprise, the present study concludes that the importance of finance in the life of an enterprise cannot be over-emphasized because a firm without adequate funds to operate will experience a limited growth.

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Recommendations

The researcher recommends that there is a need for the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) and other support agencies to provide a single-digit interest rate to MSMEs operators to ease their business operations. This is because most MSMEs cannot afford to obtain loans at exorbitant interest rates.

More so, there is a need to strengthen the Microfinance institutions to make them more readily available to assist MSMEs owners. Micro finance banks can be developed to focus mainly on rural dwellers and MSMEs whose ability to attract loans from conventional banks have been doubtful.

Further, the researcher recommends that collateral securities should be waived for MSMEs owners. The reason is simple, most MSMEs cannot afford the necessary collateral facilities to secure loans from conventional banks.

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